

Original Research

Technological and Efficiency Change of Private Hospitals in Tanzania: Does the Size Matter?

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Abstract

This study measures productivity of private hospitals in Tanzania based on the hospitals size. Specifically, the study aims at evaluating technological change and efficiency change based on hospitals' size. The study also focuses on exploring factors deriving productivity in relation to hospitals size. The study employs Malmquist productivity index (MPI) to measure and decompose productivity growth into efficiency change and technological change in relations to the hospitals size. The study used secondary data extracted from annual report of 34 private hospitals for the period ranging from 20018/19 to 2021/22. Results show that small ($0 \leq \text{beds} \leq 150$) and large hospitals ($250 \geq \text{beds}$) were experiencing productivity progress (improvement) while medium hospitals ($151 \leq \text{beds} \leq 250$) were experiencing regress over the study period. Analysis indicates that progress or regress of the hospitals was largely influenced by technical efficiency change which implies embracing or failure to embrace advanced technology, quality healthcare services, best management practices as well as investing in new operating methodologies. Large hospitals experienced deterioration in the productivity growth in year one as well as year two followed by a slight improvement in the subsequent two years. This study contributes quite relevant information for hospitals administrators and hospitals' owners as well as policy makers to make informed decision in the course of improving performance of private hospitals in Tanzania. The study also provides further guides on the efficiency utilization of the hospitals assets since the analysis is based on the size and what determine hospitals' productivity.

Keywords: Technological, Efficiency, Change, Private, Hospitals.

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Introduction

When economists refer to productivity ideally, they mean economic ability to convert inputs into outputs (Yawe, 2006). It is the performance measurement tool which represents one of the improvement strategy or targets of the firm. Literature further explained productivity as the optimal use of the firms' resources with the aim of achieving effective and efficient goals within framework of an agreed upon value systems. Broadly speaking, both in advanced as well as emerging economies productivity is regarded as the base of the economic growth and opportunity to earn competitive advantage. Therefore, productivity, efficiency as well as strategies of fostering them have gained a wide attention and become catchy concern to many researchers across the globe. According to Bwana, (2015) in health sector, assessment of hospitals performance productivity is the important step in evaluating individual performance of production units.

As contended in a study by Kao et al., (2021) in United State of America (USA) ownership of hospitals can be categorized into four, namely; private not for profit, private for-profit, federal, and state and local government hospitals. In view of the same in Tanzania category of hospitals ownership also follow the same pattern, there are private for profit (largely owned by private firms or individual), private not for profit (in most cases owned by non-government organizations or faith-based organizations), there are those owned by the central government or operate under the ministry responsible for health) and there are those which operate under the local government. Literature record that it is difficult to determine category is universally superior in terms of efficiency.

Productivity is relative term with comparison involving either the same firm (in this case hospitals) across time or between different firms (i.e. hospitals) in the same industry or firms between two industries within or between countries. The term productivity may involve partial productivity and total factor productivity (TFP), partial productivity happens when the productivity is computed based on only one factor of production (i.e. labor or capital) (for example in hospital, number of major surgeries per surgeon or number of deliveries per nurse) whereby the total factor productivity is computed when dividing total outputs by total inputs. However, productivity computations in this study premised on total factor productivity (TFP) and its components. According to (Mawson et al., n.d.) there are major four techniques of estimating the productivity and these are accounting technique; the index number technique, distance function technique and econometric technique. In Tanzania the demand for the sound and quality health care in Tanzania is increasing over time like in other developing countries where the government is facing limited funding sources to fund the increasing need, in view of the same concern private hospitals are playing a very important role to cover the shortage (Bwana, 2014).

This study applies Malmquist Total Factor Productivity index which is the distance function-based technique, since data are non-parametric Malmquist productivity index technique is suitable for the study. The study focuses on change of productivity in the private hospitals in Tanzania. The study examines productivity elasticity of 34 private hospitals in Tanzania using the Malmquist index, the measure which at the end gives technological change and technical efficiency change between 2018/19 and 2021/22 exploring the relative role of both indexes in hospital total factor productivity (TFP). Researchers in different countries have conducted studies on productivity of public

hospitals while giving little attention to the private hospitals. Just to mention, McCallion et al., (2000) used data envelopment analysis (DEA) based Malmquist productivity index (MPI) to study hospitals productivity in Northern Ireland, the hospitals under the study were assessed while keeping in view of their sizes, categorized into small and large hospitals. Their findings revealed that small hospitals achieved greater productivity gain than the large hospitals; the progression in the small hospitals it was influenced by technological change which outweighed the decline in efficiency change. In Brazil, Lobo et al., (2010) conducted similar study and employed the Malmquist DEA to evaluate the productivity change of 30 Brazilian federal university hospitals during 2003 – 2006. The result shows that University hospitals experience overall productivity growth, which solely derived by technical change (advancement in the innovation) that counterbalanced the decline in the efficiency change. According to Medarević & Vuković, (2021) it is obvious that understating of the performance of hospital systems of the country, it is very important to consider the actions of healthcare hospitals, regulations, healthcare delivery approaches, population using healthcare services as well as socio-cultural and socio-economic, factors. However, try to determine how the efficiency change and technological change affect the total productivity also remain the big challenge. However, record still show that most of the literatures on hospitals productivity emanate from developed countries, this provide solid evidence that there is limited literature regarding hospitals productivity in developing countries and Tanzania in particular. In view of the existing literature this study tries to bridge the existing gap by evaluating productivity change of private hospitals based on the hospitals' size, whereby the hospitals under scrutiny are categorized into small, medium and large hospitals. Specifically, the study focuses on:

- i. Evaluating efficiency change and technological change based on the hospitals size
- ii. Investigating factors deriving productivity in relation to hospitals size

Result from this study may be useful to decision makers in health sector including hospitals administrators to have clear knowledge on elasticity of hospitals productivity as the result of efficiency and technical change, while keeping in view the hospitals size. This would be useful when it comes to resources allocation and restructuring of the hospitals cost structure. The policy makers may also apply the report in revisiting healthcare policies with aim to ensure improvement in the health sector. The remaining part of this study is organized as follows; section two is literature review on the DEA-based Malmquist productivity change and its application on hospital industry. Section three covers data sources, variables specification and techniques involved in data analysis. Section four presents findings and discussion as well as implications of the result, and conclusion and recommendations is presented in section five.

Literature review

Fare et al., (1994) and Giuffrida (1999), Change in total factor productivity over a period of time can be derived/ influenced by: first, the technical efficiency of the firm (in this case hospitals) may change at a given scale of operation. Second, the efficiency of the firm may change in response to a change in the scale of operation. Third, the underlying technology may change and therefore derive a shift in the production frontier,

hence affect efficiency of the all organizations. In order to measure productivity, we adopted Malmquist productivity index (MPI) and its components we employ a non-parametric estimator known as data envelopment analysis (DEA). Empirical evidence shows hospitals which experience TE in the two different periods implies change in productivity between and it reflect technological change in the two periods of time, the productivity changes between the two periods of time constituted the technical change (or of shift in the frontier). Alternatively, if hospital manifest inefficiency in these two periods of time then the hospitals productivity change constituted change in outputs resulting from ‘change in efficiency’ and ‘technical efficiency’. Therefore, decomposition is very important when determining the hospitals productivity. Like in other hospitals productivity studies, this study employed DEA based MPI incorporating the decomposition approach with inputs-oriented model adopted from Färe et al., (1994). Despite existence of extensive literatures on hospitals productivity and efficiency, in developed countries few empirical studies on hospitals productivity in developing countries have been done so far. For example, Hollingsworth (2003) carried out a systematic review of literatures on hospitals efficiency and productivity have. In most of the literature reviewed by Hollingsworth, (2003) DEA and DEA – based MPI were used as the tool of analysis. Findings revealed that many studies reviewed were from developed countries.

Ouellette & Vierstraete, (2004)Malmquist productivity index (MPI) was used in evaluating the productivity of emergency departments of 15 Canadian hospitals between 1997/1998 – 1998/99. The result revealed that there was an overall regress in total productivity, which was largely derived by regress in the efficiency change which could not be counterbalanced by the small progress in the technical change improvement (innovation). The regress in the efficiency change is mainly caused by the poor management (relating to the poor coordination of the resources in relation to the level of activities of the hospital) meanwhile regress in the technical efficiency is caused by the deterioration in the technological innovation

Jacobs et al., (2006)stressed that productivity and efficiency measurements must consider the extent to which the outputs can be increased without altering the quantity of inputs. Therefore, by employing DEA based Malmquist approach we can evaluate the extent to which hospital have moved towards the best practices frontier (ECH) and whether there has been a movement in the frontier itself (TCH) over time. According to Yawe, (2006); According to Emrouznejad et al., (2008) ;Gattoufi et al., (2004) ;Seiford, (n.d.)“DEA has widely been used to estimates the MPI and technical efficiency in an environment with multiples inputs and outputs” and in particular in health sector (Grosskopf et al., 2004) ;(Hollingsworth, 2003); (Ozcan, n.d.). An index greater than one implies growth in productivity change, while a value less than one indicates a decline. If the productivity index is equal to one, it means there is neither increase nor decrease in the productivity.

Barros et al., (2008)examined 51 Portuguese hospitals in Portugal were examined using the Malmquist productivity index during(Malmquist, n.d.) 1997 to 2004. The Malmquist DEA result indicated that on average productivity of the hospitals under the study were growing, the result further exhibited the growth was largely derived by improvement in the efficiency change. In Ireland Gannon, (2008) used the DEA based

Malmquist to examined the productivity change of 36 hospitals (6 regionals, 8 general and 22 country hospitals) during 1995 – 1998. Findings revealed that on average the productivity of both regional and general were progressing while that of the country were regressing.

Dash (2009) evaluated 29 district hospitals in India using Malmquist productivity index during 2002 – 2007, the result shows increase in the overall hospitals' productivity, the increase was caused by progress in both the efficiency change and the technical change during the sampled period of study. In China, similar study was conducted by (Ng, 2008) to examine the 12 coastal hospitals and 17 inland hospitals during 2002 – 2005. Result revealed that costal hospitals were manifesting growth in productivity and their inland counterparts were experiencing the decline in the productivity. Progress in the productivity of the costal hospitals was largely caused by the advancement in the technical change which counterbalanced the decline in the efficiency change. On the other hand, the deterioration of the productivity of the inland hospitals was explained by regress in both efficiency change and technical change. Regress in efficiency change was attributed to decline in scale efficiency as well as pure efficiency.

In Botswana, Tlotlego et al., (2010) conducted similar study assessing the hospitals' productivity using a DEA based Malmquist productivity index (MPI) between 2006 - 2008, their results revealed that there was a decrease in overall productivity over the study period which was mainly derived by a substantial decline in the technical change (innovation) which could not be counterbalanced by a small improvement in the efficiency change.

Dimas et al., (2012) used DEA based Malmquist method to assess performance of 22 Greek public hospitals over 2003 -2005. Findings shows a progression in the overall productivity which primarily caused increase in the innovation which counterbalance the slight decline in the efficiency change. Decline in the efficiency change was caused by the small progress in the scale efficiency which could not be able to counterbalance the regress in the pure efficiency. With the review of literature on the nature of study and Malmquist DEA technique used covered in this part, the surveyed literature proved that hospitals productivity has been widely studied and the method has been widely used in developed countries. This justified the study to be conducted as evidence shows shortages of literature on private hospitals productivity from Tanzania. Therefore, literature indicate that increasing trend of research on efficiency of health system has been largely caused by an increase in expenditure on health and concern of quality health services (Bwana 2022).

Methodology

The study assumes that hospitals engaged in the study are operating under the same environment and that during the study period there were no any external factors that would affect the performance of the hospitals. We examined productivity of private hospitals by size, where we categorized the hospitals into three categories, small, medium and large hospitals. According to (Roh & Moon, n.d.)“hospital size can be categorized based on number of beds as follows, small hospitals $0 \leq \text{beds} \leq 130$, medium $131 \leq \text{beds} \leq 250$ and large hospitals $\text{beds} \geq 251$ ”. We had 8 small hospitals, 17 medium

hospitals, and 9 large hospitals. Data have been extracted from annual report of 34 private hospitals from the year 20018/19-2021/22. Both inputs variables and outputs variables were employed in the analysis. In selecting the outputs, we built on studies by Hu & Huang, (2004) ;Chang et al., (2011) and (Pham, 2011) the outputs used included total admission days, outpatient visits, outpatients’ surgeries, total births while inputs were total number of labors and the total number of beds. Therefore, we follow previous hospitals studies by Pham, (2011); Chen, (2006); Ferrari, (2006) where same variables were used in measuring hospitals productivity. To make sure that we avoid the possibility of having hospitals which are not efficient in the real sense (in the subset of efficient hospitals), in selecting the sample special hospitals deliberately ignored to avoid this possibility Mckillop et al., (1999).

The study adopts Malmquist DEA in examining productivity of private hospitals in Tanzania over the sampled period (20018/19 -2021/22). According to Caves et al., (1982)“productivity index can be explained as the ratios of outputs quantity index to an input quantity index. Since the study employs panel data set, Malmquist –DEA was the suitable approach to determine indices of changes in total factor productivity change (TFPCH), technical change (TECH), and efficiency change (EFFCH) and scale efficiency (SECH). The model was originally developed by Sten Malmquist, later it was advanced and enforced in measuring total factor productivity (TFP) change between two data points using ratios of distance function. The major features of MPI in productivity analysis is that it can handle multi-outputs, multi-inputs set up even in the presence of only quantity information in other words it doesn’t need the relative price information or the restrictive behavior assumptions in its formation. Building on argument of (Färe et al., 1994)the MPI application allows for the estimation of changes in overall productivity and then for decomposition into efficiency changes (ECH) and technological change (TCH) for each decision-making unit (DMUs) over time”. Efficiency change (ECH) is the result of the catch up effect, which is caused by the hospitals movement close or away from the frontier. On the other hand, technical change (TCH) is the result of the shift in the efficient frontier due to technological advancements. Malmquist productivity index (MPI) may be defined as follows:

$$M_o(x^t, y^t, x^{t+1}, y^{t+1}) = \left[\frac{D_o^t(x^{t+1}, y^{t+1}) D_o^{t+1}(x^t, y^t)}{D_o^t(x^t, y^t) D_o^{t+1}(x^{t+1}, y^{t+1})} \right]^{1/2}$$

$$M_o(y^{i+1}, x^{i+1}, y^i, x^i) = \left[\frac{D_o^{t+1}(x^{i+1}, y^{i+1})}{D_o^i(x^i, y^i)} \right] \times \left[\frac{D_o^i(x^{i+1}, y^{i+1})}{D_o^t(x^{i+1}, y^{i+1})} * \frac{D_o^i(x^i, y^i)}{D_o^{i+1}(x^i, y^i)} \right]^{1/2}$$

According to Färe et al., (1994; 1994a) “MPI can further be decomposed into efficiency change (EFFCH) and technology change (TECH) as follow:

$$EFFCH * TECH$$

Where D denotes the distance functions, M_o represents Malmquist productivity index based on output-oriented assumption. The efficiency change (**EFFCH**) represented by ratio of Farrell technical efficiency in period $t+1$ divided by Farrell technical efficiency in

period t . The technological change (**TECH**) means the geometric mean of the shift in technology as observed at (x^{t+1}, y^{t+1}) (first ratio in the bracket) and a shift in technology observed at (x^t, y^t) (second ratio inside bracket). The **EFFCH** component may take value greater than, equal to, or less than one depending on whether the efficiency of the evaluated hospital improves (catching up effect), stagnates, or declines. This will depend on the case. However, the **TECH** may also take a value greater than, equal to or less than unity in order to make the technological change positive, zero or negative respectively". An input-oriented Malmquist index was used in productivity estimates because hospitals managers and administrators have influence over the inputs resources but not the extent and type of healthcare demanded by their clients Yawe (2006); Pham (2011). This method of analyzing productivity provide platform of assessment which eventually will tell if the variations in productivity over a period of time are influenced by shifts in production technology, reflected in change in the production frontier between different periods, and changes in the technical efficiency of the hospitals under scrutiny during different time period (Cordero et al., 2021)

Results and Discussions

Hospitals were categorized into three groups based on their sizes namely; small hospitals, medium hospitals and large hospitals. The aim categorization was to determine if the size of hospitals matters when it comes to technological change and efficiency change. In establishing the category, we followed Roh & Moon, (n.d.) who classified hospitals in the group of small, medium and large based on the size/number of beds in the hospitals. (I.e. small hospitals: $0 \leq \text{beds} \leq 150$, medium: $151 \leq \text{beds} \leq 250$ and large: $\text{beds} \geq 251$). The study engaged 8 small hospitals, 17 mediums and 9 large hospitals. In the analysis of productivity growth by hospital sizes, the year 2009/2010 is considered as the reference. It is important to bear in mind that an index greater than one implies the improvement in productivity while less than one means deterioration in productivity. Generally, the drivers of total factor productivity change are efficiency change (EFFCH) and technical change (TECH). Improvement in EFFCH is considered as the catch-up effect (in this case the hospitals is trying to move towards the efficiency frontier, meanwhile the improvement in TECH is considered as the shift of the hospitals' efficiency frontier (this happens when the hospitals gain technological advancements). On the other hand, when EFFCH is deteriorating the hospitals is said to have been moving away from the efficiency frontier and vice-versa is true, while when the TECH is deteriorating it implies the hospital has failed to gain the technological advancement, to enhance the shift of its production frontier. According to Roh & Moon, (n.d.) improvement in technical change implies adoption of new technology, new healthcare services, new management systems, investing in new methodologies, etc., Meanwhile efficiency improvement indicates knowledge diffusion, market competition and cost structure as well as facility operation.

Table 1. Malmquist index for the Small, Medium and Large Hospitals

MPI & Components	Hospital size	20018/19	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	Mean
Efficiency Change (EFF CH)	Small (n=8)	0.798	1.011	1.153	0.760	0.917
	Medium (n=17)	1.115	0.830	1.191	0.565	0.888
	Large (n=9)	0.932	0.938	0.865	1.271	0.990
Technical change (TECH)	Small (n=8)	1.408	1.059	1.041	1.916	1.313
	Medium (n=17)	0.802	1.196	0.781	1.985	1.104
	Large (n=9)	1.064	0.973	1.245	0.929	1.046
Pure efficiency change (PEF CH)	Small (n=8)	0.928	1.003	1.068	0.889	0.970
	Medium (n=17)	1.035	0.973	1.246	0.978	1.053
	Large (n=9)	0.991	0.995	0.994	0.977	0.989
Scale Efficiency Change (SCECH)	Small (n=8)	0.860	1.008	1.079	0.855	0.946
	Medium (n=17)	1.078	0.853	0.956	0.577	0.844
	Large (n=9)	0.941	0.943	0.870	1.301	1.001
Total factor Productivity Change (TFP CH)	Small (n=8)	1.123	1.071	1.200	1.455	1.204
	Medium (n=17)	0.895	0.993	0.930	1.121	0.981
	Large (n=9)	0.992	0.913	1.077	1.180	1.036

Note: All Malmquist index averages are geometric means

Total-Factor Productivity (TFP) = (Technical Efficiency Change) (Technical Change)

Total efficiency change (TECH) = (Scale Efficiency Change) (Pure Efficiency Change)

Scale efficiency change (SCEF) = efficiency change/pure efficiency

Result from *Table 1* presents the TFP and its components for the small, medium and large private hospitals in Tanzania. For the calculation of total factor productivity index the year 20018/19 was taken as technology reference year in order to compute technological change over the study period (20018/19-2021/22). Figure1 presents geometric index annual productivity means of small, medium and large hospitals over the four years under consideration. The result revealed that on average over the study period total factor productivity (TFP) for the small and large hospitals were 1.204 and 1.036 respectively (improved by 20.4% and 3.6% respectively). On the other hand, that of the medium hospitals was 0.981 which implied deterioration (worsened by 1.9%). The

improvement in the productivity of small and large hospitals was mainly caused by technical change rather than efficiency change. The average progress in the technical change for the small and large hospitals was 1.313 and 1.046 respectively (growth of 31.1% and 4.6% respectively) which counterbalanced deterioration in the efficiency change of 0.917 and 0.990 respectively. On the other hand result revealed that productivity of private medium hospitals in Tanzania was deteriorating over the sampled period, TFP of 0.981 implied that on average the decrease of productivity was 1.9 % per year, the deterioration was primarily derived by substantial regress in scale efficiency 0.844 (decline by 15.6 %) which constituted deterioration in efficiency change 0.888 (decline by 11.2 %) that could not be counterbalanced by the marginal growth in technical efficiency 1.104 (increase by 10.4%). This implies that improvement in technical efficiency (TECH) 10.4% was tiny to cover the substantial deterioration in both scale efficiency and efficiency change. (*Ref. Table 1*).

The analysis of the scale efficiency change (SECH) implies that, index may be less than, equal to or greater than one if hospital's scale of operation contributes negatively, not at all or positively to hospitals productivity change (Dash, 2009); (Tlotlego et al., 2010). In line with that argument the results show that on average scale efficiency change (SECH) of small hospitals in Tanzania, for the period under the study contributed negatively to productivity change by 5.4% per year, while the average scale efficiency change (SECH) of medium hospitals contributed negatively to the productivity change by 15.6 %. On the average scale efficiency change (SECH) of large hospitals contributed positively to the productivity change of private large hospitals in Tanzania. In the study by McCallion et al., (2000) productivity of small and large hospitals in Northern Ireland, indicate that small hospitals were gaining much productivity than the larger hospitals counterparts, their findings also revealed that improvement in productivity of small hospitals which was derived by progressive shift in efficiency frontier, which outweigh decline in the efficiency. The deterioration in efficiency was primarily derived by regress in the scale efficiency. When compared to result of this study, it is contrary in sense that large private hospitals in Tanzania manifested high productivity gain than their small hospitals counterpart. Nevertheless, Deterioration of Technical efficiency and pure efficiency implies that hospitals failed to experience technical progress. As Yawe, (2006) argued, the results of technical progress should be interpreted with care, because the 'bed size' employed in different hospitals studies as proxy to capital is not a comprehensive representation of capital used by a hospital.

As Roh & Moon, (n.d.) argued, it is worth to evaluate the results in details to find out effect of technical change and efficiency change on productivity by particular group such as small, medium and large hospitals. Roh & Moon, (n.d.) evaluated productivity of non-profit hospitals in USA, where it was revealed that the geometric mean of the TFP index was 1.041 (4.1% improvement) in small-sized hospitals, 1.012 (1.2% improvement) in medium sized hospitals and 1.021 (2.1% improvement) in large sized hospitals during the study period. Meaning that small sized not-for-profit hospitals in US, were having highest productivity growth followed by large sized hospitals, while the medium sized not-for-profit hospitals experienced least productivity growth. It was also revealed that increase of productivity was largely influenced by improvement on technical change (TECH) rather than the efficiency change (EFFCH), on the contrary efficiency change (EFFCH) and its components was decreasing during the same period. Generally, the result is similar

to result found in this study, where by findings revealed that technical change (innovation) dominating the change of overall productivity of private hospitals in Tanzania. Comparing the findings of two studies result revealed that productivity growth of large hospitals in USA 2.1% was less than productivity improvement of large private hospitals in Tanzania 20.4%. On the other hand, productivity growth of non-profit small hospitals in USA 4.1% per year was higher than the productivity improvement of small private hospitals in Tanzania 3.6 % per annum. However, while the productivity of medium hospitals in USA was improving at 1.2% per year, in Tanzania the overall productivity of medium private hospitals was regressing at 1.9% per year during the period under the study.

Figure 1. Trend of Productivity change of small, medium and large hospitals

Generally, small hospitals were experiencing improvement in the productivity almost throughout the study period, while medium hospitals were experiencing regress in the productivity during the same period. Findings also revealed that there was a decline in the productivity change of large hospitals in the first two years 20018/19 and 2019/20 which was followed by an improvement in the subsequent years (*Ref. Figure 1*).

In the study by Roh & Moon (n.d.)it was found that average scale efficiency was almost less than one for all period under the study, which means that during the period under the study scale of operation of non-profit hospitals in US contributed negatively to the productivity growth of the hospitals. This conforms to the result of this study where the size of hospitals operation in the medium and small hospitals in Tanzania contributed negatively to productivity growth while in large hospitals the size of operation has positive contribution to the productivity growth. It is contended that when the scale efficiency change is greater than one it implies that hospitals' size of hospitals contributes positively to the productivity growth while less than one the hospitals' size contributes negatively. Hospitals Total factor productivity (TFP) growth is the result of the relationship between efficiency change or technical change or both, the appearing of technical efficiency as the driving factor of TFP will tell if the hospital is innovative or not. If the hospitals are innovative the source of the TFP growth will be improvement in

technical change rather than efficiency change. In case of non-innovative hospitals, however improvement in efficiency change will have positive relationship with TFP growth but very weak positive relationship between TFP and growth in technical efficiency

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study involved 34 private not-for-profit hospitals in Tanzania from 20018/19 to 2021/22, with aid of DEA-based MPI total factor productivity (TFP) index for the small, medium and large hospitals was computed. Categorization of hospitals into small, medium and large hospitals was made based on the number of hospitals' beds, and it has been considered as one of novelties of this study. Findings record that productivity of small private hospitals was progressing while that of the medium hospitals was regressing, and that progress or regress was largely influenced by technical efficiency change which implies embracing or failure to embrace new technology, new healthcare services, new management systems, investing in new methodologies. Though overall performance of medium hospitals indicate regress over the study period, it worth to note there were steady growth in annual productivity means reflected from 0.895 in the year 20018/19 to 1.121 in the year 2021/22 a growth of 22.6 percent over the study period. On the other hand, large hospitals experienced deterioration in the productivity growth in the first two years followed by an improvement in the subsequent two years. Analysis of the annual performance also indicate that in the final year 2021/22 small, medium and large hospitals were experiencing productivity growth of 45.5, 12.1 and 18.1 percent respectively. Result further revealed that there was a very weak relationship between efficiency change and TFP which indicates that hospitals under review were less effective in knowledge diffusion, market competition and cost structure as well as facility operation. Moreover, scale of operation was found to have negative contribution to the productivity improvement in small and medium hospitals. The study recommends that medium hospitals should invest much on technological change to accelerate their performance. The study recommends that while keeping up embracing of innovation and technology, private not for profit hospitals in Tanzania should also come up with new strategies on how to adopt new management knowledge, new competitive strategies as well as revisiting the cost structure of the hospitals so as to enable the hospitals to move close to the frontier (catch up effect). It is also worth to review the size of operation for the medium and small hospitals as the contribution of the said hospitals found to have negative influence to the hospitals productivity growth. The study recommends that natural extension of this works may focus on the different techniques of productivity other than DEA based Malmquist so as to have platform for comparison of the result based on the analytical techniques used. The study suggests that natural extension of this work should include alternative analytical techniques such as stochastic approach in order to provide platform for comparison of the findings obtained from different approaches (DEA based Malmquist and stochastic approach). Future studies may also consider the direction of measuring the quality of health services based on the size of the hospital under review. Future study may also focus on the performance comparison between private public hospitals so as to have basis of benchmarking the performance in the health sector.

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Abbreviations (Nomenclature)

EFFCH	The efficiency change
M_o	Malmquist productivity index based on output-oriented assumption
TECH	The technological change
(x^{t+1}, y^{t+1})	represents the unobserved individual-specific effects geometric mean of the shift in technology
(x^t, y^t)	shift in technology
DEA	Data Envelopment Analysis
MPI	Malmquist Productivity Index
TFP	Total Factor Productivity
SECH	Scale Efficiency Change

Appendix 1. Summary Statistics for Small, Medium and Large Hospitals

	Variables	Observations	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Small Hospitals (n=8) (0 ≤ beds ≤ 150)	Hospital admissions	40	4890.575	3199.322	1186	13096
	Post admissions	40	31270.03	20522.08	6460.9	91672
	Total outpatients visits	40	26189.9	20068.68	5966	62548
	Outpatient surgery	40	680.9	911.0995	0	3536
	Total births	40	818.4	854.639	120	4286
	Number of beds	40	99.875	22.4433	54	130
	Full time staffs	40	698.8	939.6889	40	2142
Medium hospitals(n=17) (151 ≤ beds ≤ 250)	Hospital admissions	85	7354.189	3797.464	249	17836
	Post admissions days	85	49115.12	68284.98	1494	362913.8
	Total outpatients	85	44560.16	69666.08	3014	362907
	Outpatients surgery	85	693.6889	1150.373	0	8900
	Total births	85	2085.456	2900.474	234	27773

	Variables	Observations	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
	Number of beds	85	175.8333	34.61352	82	265
	Full time staff	85	424.6778	696.0061	34	2217
Large hospitals (n=9) (beds ≥ 251)	Hospital admissions	45	10080.93	6775.245	1072	24060
	Post admissions	45	86759.9	102580.1	3216	600600
	Total outpatients visits	45	53776.09	45222.88	3672	141410
	Outpatient surgery	45	622.5111	577.2767	153	3536
	Total births	45	4863.911	5530.332	234	23366
	Number of beds	45	295.2222	21.65209	260	320
	Full time staff	45	779.9778	931.7628	26	2329

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